

Report Details

Report Location C:\Users\Administrator\Desktop\MARIANMARIAN 2_CHALK.pdf
Report Creator Administrator
Report Date Friday, May 31, 2024 8:58 AM

Sample Details

Sample Name CHALK
Sample Description CHALK By Administrator Date Friday, May 31 2024
Analyst Administrator
Creation Date 5/31/2024 8:53:23 AM
X-Axis Units cm-1
Y-Axis Units %T

Instrument Details

Instrument Model Spectrum Two
Instrument Serial Number 99999
Software Revision NIOS2 Main 00.02.0104 21-February-2018 16:08:00
Number of Scans 24
Resolution 4

Spectrum Graph

Name	Description
CHALK	CHALK By Administrator Date Friday, May 31 2024